

MusiCityX: Conceptual Tools for Urban Architectural Design through Music Composition

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Abstract

Architects use 3D digital design tools to explore alternative designs, but these focus on space geometry and visual design, often neglecting function and aesthetics, leading to incoherent urban forms. Based on user requirements offered by architects, this paper introduces MusiCityX, a conceptual design tool that integrates visual and auditory modalities by enabling reciprocal composition between music and architecture. It allows urban designers to create landscapes and translate architectural elements into musical footprints. Users can interact with the music resulting to architectural adjustments in real time that promote both musical harmony and urban cohesion. Expert evaluations conducted by architects indicates that MusiCityX enhances creativity by revealing hidden patterns and forming design improvements.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Interactive systems and tools**; *HCI theory, concepts and models*; • **Applied computing** → **Sound and music computing**; **Architecture (buildings)**.

Keywords

multimodal interfaces, music, interactive architecture, music translation, coherence, evaluation, digital audio workstation, spaces

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1 Introduction

Rapid urbanization has reshaped cityscapes, leading to fragmented and incoherent urban environments [11], [24], [16], [2]. In music, as in architecture, a musical part is a composition of elements. These can exist as independent pieces or as parts of larger compositions [1]. Design is an open-ended problem-solving process, bridging science and art [8], [9]. Architects use analog and digital tools—sketches, drawings, 3D models—to address urban complexity, which often lacks a unified vision [21], [19]. However, most

3D tools prioritize geometry and overlook aesthetics, functionality, and context-sensitive data essential for a holistic design [14], [26], [28]. Although multimodal and gamified approaches have emerged in collaborative planning, they remain largely visual [25], [32], with limited auditory interaction beyond voice recognition [5], [30]. Yet auditory perception plays a crucial role. Architects like Bernard Tschumi have emphasized multisensory tools to enrich design thinking [20], [7]. Projects like Steven Holl’s Stretto House, inspired by Bartók’s Music for Strings, Percussion and Celeste, and Peter Cook’s urban concept based on Bloch’s violin concerto, show how architecture and music share principles like rhythm, proportion, and harmony [31], [27]. This paper investigates how architectural design benefits from a conceptual tool that enables reciprocal translation between architecture and music. We present MusiCityX, a 3D multimodal platform that sonifies an urban Virtual Environment (UVE), allowing interactive modification of its soundscape. By converting architectural elements into musical components and vice versa, MusiCityX helps designers identify spatial dis-harmonies through their musical footprint. Users interactively refine the music and observe real-time changes in architectural parameters, resulting in harmonious music and a cohesive urban environment.

2 Related Work

Arkos Novak introduces the term archimusic to describe a fusion of architecture and music, transcending the material and auditory constraints of each domain [31]. This echoes Iannis Xenakis’ distinction between music inside-time and outside-time [6]. The dual proficiency of Xenakis in music and architecture, as well as his collaboration with Le Corbusier, led to innovations in composing in space and time. Examples include the Philips Pavilion for Expo 1958 in Brussels (Figure 1a) and the design and construction of the monastery Sainte Marie de la Tourette (Figure 1b). The Phillips Pavillion was designed by Xenakis using drawings by Le Corbusier and ended in a three-dimensional form based on the transformation of the musical designs of “Metastaseis”, the music he was working on then. [35] [29].

The challenge is to embrace the concept that architecture can lie beyond buildings and music beyond sound. Instead, their connection is articulated through a shared grammar of form, rhythm, and proportion. As Goethe described, ‘architecture is frozen music’ [15], while Vitruvius emphasized that an architect should understand music to grasp harmonic relations. Ancient Greek architects spaced columns to reflect musical intervals [15]. Early translation systems between architecture and music often relied on simplified grammars [22], [13], offering limited interactivity and overlooking the

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Figure 1: (a) Philips Pavilion. [Public domain]. (b) Sainte Marie de la Tourette. Photograph by Cemal Emden, via Divisare.

full depth of musical theory. In contrast, MusiCityX aligns architectural components with musical parameters to generate a 'musical footprint' of urban environments. Urban readability - how users perceive and navigate cities - is addressed through the influential concept of imageability by Kevin Lynch, which outlines five key urban elements: paths, edges, districts, nodes, and landmarks [3]. Although over six decades old, Lynch's framework remains widely adopted for its clarity and applicability. This study intentionally builds on Lynch's model due to its compatibility with multisensory translations such as those enabled by MusiCityX. Linear readings of urban space, such as through paths and nodes [3], [33], resonate with Xenakis' methods of translating geometry into sound. Xenakis' development of the UPIC system in 1979 further exemplifies this interdisciplinary bridge. UPIC allowed users to draw sound compositions directly, mapping time to the X-axis and pitch to the Y-axis, enabling intuitive graphical-musical translation [27], [18]. MusiCityX adopts a similar logic, integrating concepts such as paths, nodes, and landmarks into its grammar, and drawing inspiration from Xenakis' pioneering vision of spatial sound composition.

3 System Overview

The MusiCityX platform operates in four sequential stages. First, users construct the urban road network, forming the structural foundation of the virtual cityscape (Figure 2a). Second, they populate the environment by creating buildings and adding architectural elements such as windows, balconies, and doors (Figures 2b, 3a, 3b). Third, users select an urban path to be translated into music (Figure 2c). Finally, the resulting musical composition is played back,

allowing users to refine both the sound and the corresponding urban form for improved harmony (Figure 2d). The platform uses two Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs): a primary DAW for the entire musical structure (Figure 5a) and individual DAWs for each building (Figure 5b). Modifications in either DAW are immediately reflected in the urban environment, enabling real-time co-evolution of music and architecture toward a more cohesive composition.

Figure 2: Stages of the program. (a) Assemble Road System (b) Design Buildings (c) Choice of route (d) Music translation and alteration

4 Translation of Architecture to Music

Urban architecture and music rely on composition. The translation method links architectural parameters, such as the connection of a building to its surroundings, to musical characteristics, such as the harmony of a chord with a piece [23]. Each chord represents a building, as both are composite structures formed by interdependent elements, making the translation intuitive. The use of chords, a simplified structural framework from western music theory [34], [10] - was a deliberate choice to ensure accessibility for urban designers without musical training [17]. Although more intricate mappings involving complex musical events could offer greater expressive depth, they would be more appropriate for users with a musical rather than a design-oriented background. Architectural additions such as windows, doors, and balconies correspond to melodic variations, enriching the harmonic base represented by the chord of each building. These melodic elements are also played by the piano, maintaining coherence with the primary structure. A roof, as the highest architectural element, is signified by an additional note played by a violin, chosen for its distinct tone to emphasize elevation and completion. The method does not aim to disrupt urban coherence by translating an existing building into a dissonant chord. Instead, it shows how each building's chord interacts with the overall musical composition and its surrounding environment. Chords are created based on the road's layout, following music theory for context-specific translations. Design is an open-ended problem-solving process, where "accidents" can lead to innovative outcomes. MusiCityX also supports reverse translation, converting music back into architecture by mapping musical elements to architectural parameters based on their time-to-spatial relationship. Changes in musical notes prompt adjustments in architectural elements, reflecting the dynamic connection between both domains. The next section outlines the grammar and rationale of this translation.

Chords: A building's number of floors, ground floor's height, face's length and color are the architectural elements that will be translated through the chord. The 1st factor of the chord is the root note and defines only the scale. The 3rd and 5th factor affect the identity of the chord (major, minor, suspended, augmented, diminished). On top of the 5th there can be added more factors. Thereupon, we have three factors and the length of the chord to translate a building.

Color: The root note does not affect a single chord, but it affects its connection to the other chords. The corresponding architectural concept is the color that affects not just an individual building but the overall visual identity of a street. To connect color with musical notes, we categorize buildings into two groups, each corresponding to a different octave. The saturation of the color defines the brilliance and intensity of a color[4], and the average arousal ratings of a human are higher for highly saturated chromatic colors than for colors with medium or low saturation[12]. Therefore, if the saturation of the building color is greater than 0.625 ($S > 0.625$), then the building belongs to the highest octave; otherwise, if $S \leq 0.625$, it belongs to the lowest octave. The lowest octave is the 4th octave (middle octave), representing soft colors, and the highest is the 5th octave for intense colors. The first building of each category is placed first on the list and assigned the lowest frequency, note C. The next building in the same category is compared

using an algorithm based on HSV values to determine its position. If no match is found, it is assigned the last place and the highest frequency. If a match is found, each subsequent building moves one place and one note higher. The first comparison uses the HSV color model's brightness value. If the new building's brightness is greater than the old one's ($V_{\text{new}} > V_{\text{old}}$), it takes its place. If the values are equal ($V_{\text{new}} = V_{\text{old}}$), saturation is compared. If the new saturation is lower ($S_{\text{new}} < S_{\text{old}}$), it takes its frequency. If the saturation is equal, hues are compared. If the new hue is lower ($H_{\text{new}} < H_{\text{old}}$), then it takes its place. Lower hues (yellow-red) are considered more common and subtle than higher hues (magenta, blue). If hues are equal ($H_{\text{new}} = H_{\text{old}}$), the new color translates to the same note as the compared color. If any HSV value is higher, the comparison restarts for the next place.

Height of the ground floor: The height of the ground floor (HGF) changes the view of the spectator because it is at the eye level. We consider every floor height to be 3 meters and the HGF can vary from 2.5 meters to 4 meters. This means that the user has four choices (2.5 meters, 3 meters, 3.5 meters, 4 meters). The 3rd factor offers HGF translation options. It offers the same level of impact on the chord as the HGF to the urban view. To achieve this translation, we first calculate the average HGF for every road. The HGF has four options available: ($S_{\text{HGF}} = \{1,2,3,4\}$, $HGF_{\text{option}} \in S_{\text{HGF}}$). The translation function for every option is: $\text{Difference} = HGF_{\text{average}} - HGF_{\text{option}}$, $\text{PositionOfNote} = 5 - \text{Difference}$. The number 5 corresponds to the 5th note of the scale determined by the color to which the average HGF is translated.

Number of floors: The number of floors (NF) significantly impacts urban design and offers the widest range of geometric options. The 5th factor of the chord is the only option that can cover the translation of NF as it can change between four positions and additional notes can be added on top of it. MusiCityX provides options for 1 to 10 floors ($S_{\text{NF}} = \{1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10\}$). We first calculate the NF for every road. Then, we calculate the Difference between the NF of every building and the average NF: $\text{Difference} = NF_{\text{average}} - NF_{\text{option}}$. Buildings with NF equal to or one floor higher or lower than the average ($-1 \leq \text{Difference} \leq 1$) will be translated through the function $\text{PositionOfNote} = 8 - \text{Difference}$ that defines the position of the chord's 5th factor. The number 8 is the 8th note of the scale in which the average NF will be translated. Buildings with NF more than one floor higher than the average ($NF_{\text{option}} > NF_{\text{average}} + 1$) will be translated by adding additional notes at the top of the chord. The top factor of the chord will remain the 9th note of the scale $\text{PositionOfNote} = 9$, and then, depending on the Difference value, one to four extra notes will be added to the chord. In this way, even if the average NF is one floor and the building to translate has ten floors, translation is still possible. However, buildings with an NF more than one floor lower than the average ($NF_{\text{option}} < NF_{\text{average}} - 1$) cannot be translated using just the chord, as this could disrupt the chord's structure. Therefore, these buildings will be translated with the help of an extra note before the chord. The top factor's position will stay to the 7th note $\text{PositionOfNote} = 7$, and the extra note will start from also 7th and will diminish depending on the Difference $\text{PosExtraNoteBefore} = 9 - |\text{Difference}|$. This function will be applied if $|\text{Difference}| \geq 2$. That is why the number 9, exists to the position of the extra note, to remove this

Difference and start the extra note from the 7th note. MusiCityX allows users to add a roof, which adds an extra note as the 1st note of the chord, played by a violin. Each side of a corner building can generate a different chord.

Melody: The doors will be represented by the same note as the 1st factor of the chord, the balconies by the 3rd factor, and the windows by the 5th factor. The duration of each note depends on the element’s length, and the note’s position on the chord corresponds to the element’s position along the building’s x-axis.

Inversion from music to refined architecture: During the translation from urban design to music, users adjust the resulting musical piece based on musical principles and personal preferences. These changes are reflected back in urban design through reverse translation. Most parameters follow a direct mapping, but color—defined by Hue, Saturation, and Value (HSV)—is more arbitrary. When a note’s pitch changes, the system first searches for an existing color associated with the new note. If found, it applies that color; if not, it looks for an intermediate note to blend colors. If no match exists, and the note is at an extreme (highest or lowest), the color becomes lighter or darker accordingly.

5 Implementation

We now describe the design process using our system which comprises of four stages.

Stage1 - Assemble Road System: The user creates a road or road network by pressing the "New Road" button, with a pre-fab road attached to the cursor (Figure 2a). The rotation of the road can be adjusted. The first road can be placed anywhere, but subsequent roads must connect to an existing one to form turns.

Stage2 - Design Buildings: The user creates buildings and adds windows, doors, balconies, and balcony doors, along with building variables (Figure 3a). By pressing the "Build it" button, the instantiated building attaches to the cursor (Figure 2b) and is placed near a road or road turn. After placing the building, the user can click on a side to add elements (windows, doors, balconies, balcony doors) and adjust the floor’s position using keyboard strokes (Figure 3b).

Stage3 - Choice of route: The user selects the roads to compose the path to be translated to music by pressing the white cubical buttons that appear on top of each road section (Figure 2c).

Stage4 - Music translation and alteration: When the user presses the "Music" button to enter the final stage, the music translation occurs. The user listens to the musical piece and makes adjustments to create a more coherent composition (Figure 2d). The platform guides the user through four stages, gradually revealing the central menu. The user progresses through each stage until the fourth menu is activated, as shown in Figure 4.

5.1 DAWs on the stage of music

The final stage’s interface is split into two sections (Figure 5a): the top 75% allows navigation and interaction in the urban environment, while the bottom 25% displays the main Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) to listen to the full musical theme and edit chord positions and durations linked to building placement and scale. Clicking a building reveals its individual DAW (Figure 5b), showing detailed notes for chord and melody. Users can modify the Number of Floors (NF), Height Gain Factor (HGF), color, and architectural elements.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: (a) Building Control Panel (b) Adding elements UI

Figure 4: The development of the central menu

Changes to chords update associated melody notes, and adjustments to corner buildings affect adjoining sides accordingly.

6 Evaluation

16 architecture students (4 graduate, 12 undergraduate) participated in the evaluation. After a tutorial video, they completed two progressively complex tasks designed to assess user interaction with the MusiCityX platform.

Task 1: Participants were instructed to create a road and a building between one and three floors. They were encouraged to explore all available musical modifications, accompanied by an explanation of the theoretical framework.

Task 2: This required users to construct a street with multiple low-rise buildings and at least one building that spanned seven

(a) Urban scenery and main DAW

(b) Individual and main DAW

Figure 5: Music stage's DAWs

floors, all in a uniform soft color. Unlike Task 1, no guidance was provided, allowing observation of the independent interaction. Participants evaluated the resulting musical footprint, identifying coherence issues emerging from the overall composition rather than individual chords. This led to an understanding of how spatial design influences musical harmony, and users made architectural changes to improve both.

Qualitative Findings: Certain users had initial difficulties with camera movement and building placement, but this was resolved by the time of the second task. Some noted similarities to Twinmotion, though most found the interface distinct, which they appreciated given the tool's unique purpose. The dynamic step-by-step menu was praised as intuitive and supportive. Coherence issues emerged not as a single wrong chord, but as a subtle strangeness in the overall musical theme, which some users associated with jazz. This preserved artistic freedom and several participants claimed they would use the tool to create both coherent but also intentionally unconventional designs.

Quantitative Questionnaire: The participants filled out a three-part questionnaire. The first assessed their background, revealing that 25% had moderate to advanced musical knowledge. The second employed the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) to measure mental demand, performance, effort, and frustration: 80% rated mental demand at or below 5/10, 95% reported high performance, and most reported low effort and frustration, with two-thirds noting no frustration. The third section addressed usability: 90% rated the difficulty of the interface as below average, while 90% also rated MusiCityX as highly successful (9–10/10), describing it as intuitive and manageable. Musical translations followed classical theory, producing coherent harmonies that could be refined. Incoherence appeared in the overall musical flow rather than in specific chords, preserving creative freedom. Both trained and untrained

users identified and resolved incoherence, demonstrating the broad accessibility of the tool.

7 Conclusion

This paper introduced MusiCityX, a multimodal design tool that translates urban environments into music to help detect and address spatial incoherence. Unlike mathematical problems, architectural design lacks a single correct solution, making tools that support creative exploration especially valuable. MusiCityX enables users to identify inconsistencies and experiment with new forms, including intentional distortions in both visual and auditory domains. While music and architecture share compositional principles, their translation has limits. Not all spatial complexities can be meaningfully expressed through sound, and overuse of musical analogies risks oversimplification. Still, MusiCityX shows that sound can enhance spatial awareness without constraining artistic freedom.

Future improvements could include scene saving, audio exporting, and added urban features like curvature, traffic elements, and citizen movement. The translation algorithm could also integrate musical styles—matching architectural eras with genres (e.g., Baroque for 18th-century buildings)—to enrich the experience. MusiCityX may also serve educational purposes by offering an engaging way to explore spatial coherence and design principles. By linking vision and sound, the system fosters a new mode of urban thinking—one where cities can not only be seen, but also heard.

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